

Real broadband for the aviation industry

WWRF 50th meeting

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Introducing SkyFive

We bring broadband to every aircraft

Who we are

- Provider of broadband to commercial aircraft, business jets, helicopters, and drones
- Spun off from Nokia in 2019
- Builders of European Aviation Network, world's largest A2G network for commercial aviation
- Driving the proliferation of A2G in Middle East, India, Southeast Asia, China, and Oceania
- Financed by Safran and other institutional investors
- Strong industrial partners from aviation and telecommunications
- Headquartered on the campus of Airbus in Munich, Germany

A2G (Air-to-Ground): fastest, smallest, and cheapest solution for inflight connectivity

Proven in Europe

1

seamless
network

41

countries
covered

5

airlines using
the service

300+

Aircraft
connected

< 8 hrs

installation
time

100+

PAX per flight
going online

85 mn

Internet
sessions

fully
certified

First aircraft connected in the Middle East

“ Highly satisfied with video streaming and web browsing - the experience was perfect!
([link*](#))

*Start watching at 06:02:02.

One network serves all aircraft

Optimized for domestic and continental routes, which constitute 80-90% of traffic

Many aircraft types

Various A2G terminals

One network for all

